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Regional Security and National Development in Africa: A Survey of Selected States

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Abstract

The onset of a new and emerging threat to peace, development, and security in the African region has unfortunately added other strands of threat to national security in most African states and Africa as a whole. Security of life and property has long been a part of human existence and could be aptly viewed as freedom from threat or violence. Durable peace and regional security have remained elusive in most African states. The very nature and character of the African states, which were embedded in colonial origins, have led to manifestations of insecurity and violence in different trends in almost all African states. The purpose of this study is therefore to explore the approach of the African region to its regional security and national development management strategies. Historical and descriptive methods of data analysis were used. The study unfolds the concept of regional security and economic development and the security threat facing Africa, which included radical Islam, natural resource discoveries, ethno-religious conflicts, and political-based violence, among others. The impact of insecurity on Africa's economic development was succinctly explored to show that the increasing challenge of insecurity in Africa has been linked to the failure of leadership to deliver good governance and secure the welfare of persons on the principles of freedom, equality, and justice, which negates the regional security and national development of most African States.

Keywords: National development security, insecurity, good governance.

Introduction

Extreme poverty, political and economic marginalisation, poor governance, and a lack of access to opportunities are not only challenges that millions of Africans face but also fertile breeding grounds for threats such as civil conflicts, extreme terrorism, and

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uncontrolled migration (Sibry T. 2010). Since the publication of the United Nations' 'A more secure world report', threats to one are increasingly threats to all. The growth of fundamentalism in one region affects other regions in the form of export of terrorism, massive internal displacements, and the overflow of refugees. Similarly, poverty and poor health infrastructure in one region can lead to pandemics that easily reach other regions.

Security can no longer be effectively addressed from the traditional state-centric perspective, where national security and law enforcement apparatus are all that are needed to ensure the security of citizens. Instead, security has become global, with a focus on individuals and groups accessing the benefits of development, a more people-centred security. The growing concept of 'human security' therefore underlines the importance of empowering individuals and groups to benefit from economic growth and development, so as to not only protect them from conflicts and tension but also to build their resilience to engage in development activities. There can be no peace without development, and equally, no sustained development can take place without peace.

Security and political stability therefore have to be anchored on the availability of institutional capacities, opportunities, and decent standards of living. Indeed, countries with high inequality and weak institutions often have high levels of social violence (AfDB, 2019). Poor distribution of wealth, insufficient economic opportunities, jobs, and limited freedom, particularly for a large young population, significantly increase the risk of instability. Such societies tend to be far more affected by transnational and organised crime, which in turn slows down the national development efforts of any state.

While acknowledging the limitations of the divide between humanitarian and development approaches in responding to the security and development challenges facing Africa, there is a need for caution. Specifically, we must recognise that violent conflict is the manifestation of fragility, whose drivers need to be clearly identified. And on this, the paper is centred.

Conceptual Clarification

Concept of Regional Security

Security is a fragile and significant issue that conveys different meanings to different

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scholars, analysts, policymakers, and organisations across the globe. In other words, the meaning of security attracts different meanings and different views. Accordingly, the elastic nature of the concept attracts different meanings and perceptions among writers. Fundamentally, security has to do with the presence of peace, safety, gladness, and the protection of human and physical resources. It entails the absence of crises or threats to human dignity, all of which facilitate the development and progress of any human society. It has to do with the process connected with assuaging any kind of threat to people and their precious values. To Buzan (1991), security is about freedom from threat and the ability of states to maintain their independent identities and territories.

The UNDP identifies two main aspects of the concept. In the first place, it means “safety from such chronic threats as hunger, disease, and repression.” In its other dimension, “it means protection from sudden and hurtful disruptions in the patterns of daily life” (UNDP, 1994: 23). According to the Human Security Commission, human security is defined by its aims: to protect the vital core of human lives in ways that enhance human freedoms and human fulfillment. Human security means protecting fundamental freedoms—freedoms that are the essence of life. It means protecting people from critical (severe) and pervasive (widespread) threats and situations (Commission on Human Security, 2003: 4).

Regional security, on the other hand, entails a group of states whose primary security concerns link together sufficiently closely that their national security cannot realistically be considered apart from one another (Buzan, 1991). It is seen as a set of peace and security relations that occur in a broad territory (region), driven by agents operating at various levels of regional integration who use various instruments to change the patterns of security, conflict, and positive peace.

Another link between regionalism and security concerns the regional implications of a local conflict. These depend on the nature of the security complex and the way various security problems are vertically and horizontally linked in particular regions, which can be highly varying. Accordingly, in a bid to ensure peace-building, regional security, and regional cooperation within the African continent, several agencies and organisations have been institutionalised to handle conflict, crises, and war within the region; these include the African Union (AU), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), ECOWAS, ECOMOG, the EU, and SADC, among others. Through these agencies and organisations, Africa as a region has been able to come

together in one-fold to address most security challenges and issues surrounding the region as a continent in order to ensure effective economic development.

Concept of Economic Development

The concept of "development" is variously defined. It implies progress—an observable or noticeable improvement in the socio-economic and cultural lives of the people towards their wellbeing, welfare, or emancipation. In this light, according to Chandler (2007), development is seen as a broader concept that recognises psychological and material factors that measure human well-being. Development, therefore, is a multifaceted phenomenon and man-centred. It is the process of empowering people to maximise their potential and develop the knowledge capacity to exploit nature to meet daily human needs (Ake, 2001). The transformation of society and the emergence of new social and economic organisations are critical indicators of development (Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013).

Seers (1994) defined development as a multidimensional process involving the reorganisation and reorientation of the entire economic and social system. It involves improvements in income and output, changes in institutional, social, and administrative structures, as well as changes in popular attitudes, customs, and beliefs. Omale and Ebiloma (2005) defined development as a process by which the efforts of the people are united with those of the government or other organisations to improve the economic, social, and cultural condition of communities, to integrate these communities into the life of the nation, and to enable them to contribute fully to the nation's progress.

Economic development, on the other hand, refers to economic transformation that influences the living standards of people in society. It entails the structural transformation of an economy by introducing more mechanised and updated technologies to increase labour productivity, employment, incomes, and the standard of living of the population. The concept is accompanied by improvements in infrastructure as well as social, political, and institutional factors to facilitate the transformation of the economy (Myint and Krueger 2016).

Socio-economic development is a product of development and can be defined as the process of social and economic transformation in a society. Socio-economic development embraces changes taking place in the social sphere, mostly of an economic

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nature. Thus, socio-economic development is made up of processes caused by exogenous and endogenous factors, which determine the course and direction of development. Socio-economic development is measured with indicators such as GDP, life expectancy, literacy, and levels of employment.

According to Gillis et al. (1983), economic development refers to a rise in national or per capita income, with or without structural changes in the economy. It refers to fundamental changes in the structure of the economy, capital structure, institutional framework, and infrastructure in order that the majority of the population can achieve a high standard of living. The concept aimed at achieving high standards of living, changes in capital structure, therefore calls for changes in the structure of capital goods, as this is basic for the transformation of primary producing economies, using labour-intensive techniques in general, with large scale unemployment and poverty, to a fully employed and developed economy using the latest capital-intensive methods of production.

Accordingly, economic development is regarded as important for a country to reduce its poverty by providing more employment, higher incomes, improved goods and services, and the latest technologies of production. The crux of the problem, however, is that the framework for economic development—modern technology, the industrial sector, and infrastructural facilities—has not yet been established in many countries around the world due to various historical and political reasons. Hence, there is a high level of inequality among, and even within countries.

To Nwanegbo and Odigbo (2013) and Chandler (2007), development cannot be achieved in any nation where there are conflicts, crises, and war. There is a consensus in the literature that security and development are two different and inseparable concepts that affect each other, and this has naturally triggered debates on the security-development nexus (Chandler, 2007; Stan, 2004).

Factors that Aid Economic Development

A couple of measures, as posited by Kula (2007), have been articulated as ways by which economic development could occur holistically or in a more integrated manner in the LDCs.

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- i. **Political Stability:** This atmosphere attracts both foreign and local investors to a country.
- ii. **Leadership:** This type of leadership a country has to an extent determines very much the rate of her economic development.
- iii. **Diversification of the Economy:** This will make a country not to depend on a particular sector of her economy and facilitates her economic development.
- iv. **Mechanization of Agriculture:** This will make small percentage of the population to be producing enough food for the teeming population while others will be utilised in other areas of economic development.
- v. **Industrialization:** This is associated with development because almost all developed countries of the world are industrialized with modern and new technology.
- vi. **Availability of Capital:** This can be achieved through prudent use of resources and increase the national saving, including cutting down on present consumption in order to increase saving and investment by individuals.
- vii. **Medical Facilities:** Health is said to be wealth and the health of the citizens is the wealth of the nation.
- viii. **Optimum Population and Human Capital Development:** If the population of a country grows at the same rate with the national resources, economic development can be achieved in a short period of time; and this is in addition to the development of available human resources with the needed critical skills.
- ix. **Level of Literary:** The more of educated people a country has, the more manpower the country will get and the faster it will be for economic development to take place.
- x. **Infrastructural Facilities:** These are facilities like good roads, sea and airports, iron and steel complexes, etc.
- xi. **Right Attitude to Work:** If worker, as executors of economic plan, show right or positive attitude to work, economic development will be achieved in a short period of time.
- xii. **Prudent Use of Financial Resources:** Good and judicious use of a country's financial resources is necessary to aid economic development.

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Measurement of Economic Development

There are yardsticks or indices to be used in measuring any country's economic development and to rank countries in terms of their economic achievement.

a. Per Capita Income (PCI)

Economic development is assumed to take place when there is a rise in the standard of living of the population. Real per capita income is assumed to be the best index for depicting the average standard of living of the population, and so it is widely used as an index of economic development. According to the UN, "We had some difficulty in interpreting the term underdeveloped countries. We use it to mean countries in which PCI is low when compared with the PC real income of the USA, Canada, Australia, and Western Europe." (Higgins, 1963).

b. Per Capital Output

Lewis (1955), cited in Panth (2020), also considered per capita output to be one of the best single measures of economic development. Accordingly, based on this, the World Bank classifies countries based on their gross national income per capita (the least developed country category). Earlier, gross national income (GNI or GNP) was estimated using simple exchange rates to convert the currencies of various countries into US dollars. At present, the World Bank uses the Atlas conversion factor instead of simple exchange rates, mainly to reduce the impact of exchange rate fluctuations in the cross-country comparison of national incomes. The Atlas conversion factor for any year is the average of a country's exchange rate for that year and its exchange rates for the two preceding years, adjusted for the difference between the rate of inflation in the country and international inflation. The objective of the adjustment is to reduce any changes to the exchange rate caused by inflation.

c. Structural change in the production method

However, industrialization and capital formation are often used synonymously with structural changes in production methods. The structural changes in production methods imply the use of capital-intensive methods of production in place of the hitherto labour-intensive techniques. With more capital-intensive techniques, the productivity of labour increases, leading to an increase in output and growth. Most theories of development deal with various methods by which the growth of the capital base of less developed

countries can be achieved. A number of studies have been undertaken historically to estimate the changing structure of developing economies by comparing the growth of different sectors of the economy, such as primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors. (Herrendorf et al., 2013).

By so doing, the economic development of any country therefore calls for changes in the structure of capital goods, as this is basic for the transformation of primary producing economies, using labour-intensive techniques in general, with large scale unemployment and poverty, to a fully employed and developed economy using the latest capital-intensive methods of production.

d. Improvement in Human Status

Interestingly, other than a mere increase in material output, development should also improve the human status of the population (Todaro, 1994). For example, Goulet (1971) identifies three basic and interconnected components, or core values, in the wider meaning of development. They are as follows:

- i. **Life sustenance:** to satisfy the basic needs of the population – income, food, clothing, housing, minimal education, and health facilities in order to raise the people above the poverty line.
- ii. **Self-esteem:** countries that are exploited by other countries, or dominated by them, cannot maintain their self-respect. They need to free themselves from such dependence and achieve self-respect and independence.
- iii. **Freedom:** from the three evils of want, squalor, and ignorance. Development allows choice as it expands the range of human activity of education, employment, livelihood, mobility, as well as material goods.

e. Poverty Index

The absolute levels of poverty, i.e., the absolute income level of the lowest 41%, are sometimes taken as indicators of development. For this index to be meaningful, it is necessary to have a standard minimum income to compare the incomes of the poor. In India, a “poverty line” was constructed, measuring the level of income at which the average family consumes a nutritious diet defined in terms of calories. (Dandekar and Rath, 1971). The World Bank's International Poverty Line, 1981, takes the number of people consuming “less than \$1 per person, per day” as an indicator of poverty levels. In 2013, this was increased to \$1.90 per day. Recently, estimates for global poverty state that 8.6% of the world, or 736 million people, live in extreme poverty on \$1.90 or less a

day, according to the World Bank. Hence, whenever the citizens live within the above definition, that entails that economic development has not taken place.

Security Threats Facing Africa

African states have faced several security challenges and threats since their independence. Some of these threats will be discussed below.

i. Radical Islam

Radical Islam is a global phenomenon generated by the uncontrolled dissemination of extremist ideology, supported by vast private wealth in the Gulf, the use of which is not subject to scrutiny. It poses a distinctive threat to Africa, partly because many African countries have substantial Muslim populations that, in conditions of poverty and poor governance, can easily become disaffected. Additionally, the threat is distinctive because the organisations needed to counter it effectively require a level of sophistication and cost that are beyond the means of most African militaries.

The threat from radical Islam has recently been evident in Mali, the Central African Republic (CAR), Kenya, and Nigeria. In Mali and CAR, it was existential: without timely French military intervention, both states would have been overrun and fallen to radical Islamic forces. In Nigeria and Kenya, the threat has taken the form of sensational terrorism that, while not threatening the states themselves, is highly damaging to their international reputations. This difference in consequences is primarily due to the greater military capacity of Nigeria and Kenya; both countries have economies that are sufficiently robust to finance militaries with the capacity to defeat feasible rebel challenges.

However, their security forces are not adequate for the more demanding task of preventing the escalation of terrorism. In all four situations, Islamic terrorism is a spillover from failing neighbouring countries in which Islamic militants have been able to build their military capacity. The meltdown in Libya, which is ongoing, provided a base from which a rebel force could equip itself sufficiently to defeat the Malian army; the endemic insecurity of vast areas of the Sahel enabled a rebel force to defeat the army of CAR and to infiltrate north-east Nigeria; and Islamists in Somalia were able to mount terrorist attacks in Kenya. Geography, more than policy differences, probably accounts for why it is these countries and not others that are facing the worst threats: these countries border on failing states. But there is clearly the potential for terrorism to spread.

ii. Natural Resource Discoveries

Although Africa has long been a natural resource exporter, until recently it was only as lightly prospected-resource extraction per square mile was much lower in other regions. The high commodity prices of the past decade have triggered a wave of investment in prospecting, and because Africa was the least explored region, it became the preferred location for exploration. During the past decade, many valuable resources have been discovered in previously resource-poor African countries, often in remote areas.

During the present decade, mines and transport infrastructure will be developed in order to exploit these discoveries. While natural resources have the potential to finance development, they also have the potential to catalyse violent conflict. Valuable resources have sometimes been a source of Rwandan soldier stands guard at Bangui M'Poko International Airport in CAR finance for rebel groups, as with diamonds in Angola and Sierra Leone. They have also raised the stakes for capturing power while reducing the need for accountability to citizens by displacing taxes as the primary source of state revenue. The resulting contamination of politics has long been illustrated by Nigeria.

Further, since valuable resources are never evenly spread throughout a territory, they give well-endowed regions an incentive to try to secede from the nation, as with the Katanga region of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) and the Biafra region of Nigeria. The localised nature of resource discoveries interacts with strong sub-national identities to create serious security vulnerabilities. The same national and sub-national identities can be entirely compatible in the context of cooperation but become antagonistic once the ownership of valuable resources becomes salient. This is by no means Africa-specific; Scotland is an example. For three centuries, being Scottish was not seen as incompatible with being British; for much of this period, the most salient activity was the common task of defence against external threats. However, during the past decade of high oil prices, the oil off the shore of Scotland has replaced external security as the most salient issue, leading to strong pressure for secession. Because African sub-national identities are so strong, this interaction of resources and local identity is likely to be particularly troubling in the region.

The recent oil discovery in Kenya is located in a remote area whose people, the Turkana, have never been integrated into Kenyan identity. Oil activities soon had to be suspended due to local violence. Even in Tanzania, the discovery of gas offshore in the

region of Mtwara led to riots and four deaths because people in the region claimed that it belonged to them, not to the nation. Currently, South Sudan has collapsed into civil war because the oil, which is the government's sole source of finance, is located in the territory of the Nuer tribe, whereas the government is controlled by the Dinka, their ancestral rivals.

iii. Weakness of state and chaos zones

The weakness of states and chaos zones are factors that contribute to the security threats in most African countries. Sadly, since most states have no power or control over their entire territory, most states are permeable to germinate and develop in the most diverse ways of subversion (Garcia and Ferro, 2013). This combination may further undermine the already fragile existence of these countries as a political reality.

Consequently, there are numerous regional conflicts that spread across the African space, and just to name the most relevant ones, besides those related to Daesh, which is affirmed as a subversive phenomenon on a global scale: In North Africa, the issue of Western Sahara status, conflicts in Libya, Mali, and all manifestations of instability and insecurity in the Sahel are highlighted, where problems must always be seen as cross-border and interrelated; in sub-Saharan Africa, we highlight all the conflict in Nigeria, both around the Niger Delta and Boko Haram, which, in addition to destabilising northwestern Nigeria, has spread to Cameroon, Chad, and Niger; and we cannot fail to mention the humanitarian disaster in the Democratic Republic of Congo, where violence is endemic, and the problem of Cabindan secessionism, still unresolved in Angola, which has guerrilla purses still active in the territory.

Armed conflicts also provoke a sea of refugees who live in camps where poverty is usually high and prophylactic care is diminishing. In addition to all this, in Africa, there are economic disparities, climate change, and exponential population growth. This culture broth arouses factors that eventually promote irregular migration, forcing people to move to other spaces in search of resources, security, and well-being, weakening territories and the sense of space, “devaluing states in the logic of their constitutive elements and perhaps valuing others; in fact, nothing new, with due adaptations” (Dias, 2016).

Africa experiences all kinds of population movements, interregional and

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intraregional, including mixed and irregular migration, labour migration, and displacement due to conflict and natural disasters. The International Organisation for Migration (IOM) accounts for 16 million migrants (IOM, 2018), and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees accounts for 10 million displaced persons and seven million refugees on the continent, about one-third of the total in the world. world (UNHCR 2017). The migratory factor (as a source of tension and some instability), with the flow oriented predominantly to Western countries, where the new communities that settle down are hardly integrated into local societies, enhances the disenchantment and potential affiliations and combatants for the alternative presented by global subversion.

Accordingly, irregular migration, which the Transnational Criminal Organisations (OCT) take advantage of, leads to the exploitation of human misery. Let us look at the dramatic situations of those who seek in the European Eldorado a golden misery. In the *pateras* heading towards the northern shores of the Mediterranean or the Canaries, we meet people from all over the African continent. They come mainly from West Africa but also from Sudan, Chad, the Horn of Africa, and even Southern Africa. The IOM considers three main routes: the North African route (from sub-Saharan Africa to North Africa and Europe); the Gulf of Aden route (from the Horn of Africa to Yemen and beyond); and the southern route (from the east and the horn of Africa to South Africa and beyond). These migrants, in search of security and well-being, are at great risk. Many of those who fail remain in transit countries, which eventually become destinations. They get older and phase out their “jumping operation,” which also allows them to have several informal jobs during the trip, which will ensure them the next step. This is a daily phenomenon, and millions of desperate people seek to reach the other side of the stability frontier, where order is still felt. The TCBs, with the funds generated, acquire a level of power that competes with some of the African states. They express this power by their ability to create various forms of instability in the countries in which they operate, broad-spectrum instability from the social to the economic, from the political to the psychological. At the same time, they try to indirectly gain political power through the corruption of their sovereign bodies and their officials in order to intimidate the established power and guarantee complete freedom of action in their criminal activities. This further weakens the already weak state structures.

In West Africa, a region where most countries are among the poorest in the

world, drug trafficking is valued at hundreds of millions of dollars. Narcotics trafficking networks often take advantage of structural weaknesses in countries such as Guinea-Bissau and, with the approval of local ruling elites, have turned the region into a significant transit hub for Europe's distribution route.

vi. Ethno-religious Conflicts

These conflicts are caused by suspicion and distrust among various ethnic groups and among the major religions in the country. Ethno-religious conflict is a situation in which the relationship between members of one ethnic or religious group and another of such group in a multiethnic and multi-religious society is characterised by a lack of cordiality, mutual suspicion and fear, and a tendency towards violent confrontation (Achumba et al., 2013; Salawu, 2010). The frequent and persistent ethnic conflicts and religious clashes between the two dominant religions (Islam and Christianity) are a major security challenge that confronts Africa and Nigeria in particular. Since independence, most African countries appear to have been bedevilled with ethno-religious conflicts. There are ethno-religious conflicts in all parts of the region, and these have emerged as a result of new and particularistic forms of political consciousness and identity often structured around ethno-religious identities (Ibrahim and Igbuzor, 2002).

Ethno-religious violence is also traceable to the inability of African leaders to tackle development challenges and distribute state resources equitably. Other causes are accusations of neglect, oppression, domination, exploitation, victimisation, discrimination, marginalisation, nepotism, and bigotry. For example, in Nigeria, ethno-religious conflicts have assumed alarming rates. It has occurred in places like Shagamu (Ogun State), Lagos, Abia, Kano, Bauchi, Nassarawa, Jos, Taraba, Ebonyi, and Enugu State, respectively. These ethno-religious identities have become disintegrative and destructive social elements, threatening peace, stability, and security in Nigeria (Eme and Onyishi, 2011).

v. Politically Based Violence

Africa has a long history of politically-based violence since its independence. The electoral politics in the region have been characterised by violent conflicts, political thuggery, assassinations, and arson. Politicians in Africa do not accommodate dialogue, negotiation, and consensus (Eme and Onyishi, 2011). Political contests are

characterised by desperation and a violent struggle for political power among politicians. Recurring political violence in Africa could be attributed to over-zealousness and desperation of political gladiators to win elections or remain in office at all costs. These misadventures have often been catastrophic, leading to the decimation of innocent lives, disruption of economic activities, and the destruction of properties, among others.

vi. Systemic and Political Corruption

This is a twin-evil, hydra-headed monster that has held the African state captive. This has contributed to government failure and the breakdown of institutional infrastructure. The state of insecurity in Africa is largely a function of government failure, traceable to systemic and political corruption. It has added another dimension to violent conflicts, which has eroded national values. Corruption is bad not because money and benefits change hands or because of the motives of participants, but because it privatises valuable aspects of public life, bypassing processes of representation, debate, and choice. It has been described as a cancer militating against Africa's development because corruption deeply threatens the fabric of African society (Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013). Accordingly, corruption hampers economic growth, disproportionately burdens the poor, and undermines the effectiveness of investment and aid (Iyare, 2008).

vii. Economic-Based Violence

This is also referred to as the "political economy of violence." Eme and Onyishi (2011) note that, in recent writings in the mass media, much emphasis has been laid on the role of resources in generating conflict, which is a major cause of economic-based violence across the globe and across political divides. Cries of resource control and revenue sharing regularly rent the air between proponents and opponents, also leading to violent agitations among the contending actors and between the state and proponents. The Niger-Delta crisis in Nigeria presents a classic case of this violent struggle that has been on since the end of the Nigerian civil war in 1970. These violent agitations have claimed the lives of many Nigerians and foreigners, military and paramilitary personnel, and properties worth billions of naira. It has also resulted in economic misfortune in Nigeria through the loss of oil revenue as a result of a shortfall in crude oil exports by the oil companies, occasioned by the disruption of oil exploration activities by the Niger-Delta militants.

Although by no means limited to oil in the Niger Delta, the most prevalent campaign about the link between resources and conflict in Nigeria focuses on oil and the Delta region. No doubt oil has given rise to vertical and horizontal conflicts between the national, state, and society, or between dominant and subordinate geopolitical zones, classes, and groups across Nigeria, given the pivotal role that oil plays in the political economy and power relations in Nigeria. It is, however, true that other types of resource-driven conflicts have received less attention in the debate. Assets such as grazing, farming, and water resources have tended to give rise to horizontal conflicts that involve communities across the geopolitical zones.

viii. Pervasive Material Inequalities and Unfairness

A major factor that contributes to insecurity in Africa is the growing awareness of inequalities and disparities in life chances, which lead to violent reactions by a large number of people. There is a general perception of marginalisation by a section of the people in areas of government development policies and political patronage, and these are triggers of disaffection, resentment, and revolt (Achumba et al., 2013). The incessant strikes by labour and professional groups and demonstrations by civil society groups are mainly due to pervasive material inequalities and unfairness. Their agitations are aimed at drawing public sympathy for their struggle for just and fair treatment by the government.

ix. Unemployment/Poverty

Unemployment and poverty among Africans, especially among the youth, are major causes of insecurity and violent crimes in the region (Adagba et al., 2012). Youth's unemployment has contributed to the rising cases of violent conflict in the region. Also, one of the major causes of insecurity in the country is the failure of successive administrations to address the challenges of poverty, unemployment, and the inequitable distribution of wealth among ethnic nationalities.

x. Porous Borders

Achumba et al. (2013) observe that the porous frontiers of the region, where individual movements are largely untracked, have contributed to the level of insecurity in Africa. As a result of the porous borders, there is an unchecked inflow of small arms and light

weapons into countries, which has aided militancy and criminality (Hazen and Horner, 2007). For instance, in Nigeria, available data show that the country hosts over 70 percent of about 8 million illegal weapons in West Africa (Edeko, 2011). Also, the porosity of the Nigerian borders has aided in the uncontrollable influx of migrants, mainly young men, from neighbouring countries such as the Republic of Niger, Chad, and the Republic of Benin, responsible for some of the criminal acts (Adeola and Oluyemi, 2012).

xi. Terrorism

The most fundamental source of insecurity in Africa today is terrorism, which is traceable to religious fanaticism and intolerance, particularly in Islam-dominated states of Africa (Achumba et al. 2013). Terrorism is a global phenomenon, and it is ravaging the whole world. It has been defined by Sampson and Onuoha (2011) as “the premeditated use or threat of use of violence by an individual or group to cause fear, destruction, or death, especially against unarmed targets, property, or infrastructure in a state, intended to compel those in authority to respond to the demands and expectations of the individual or group behind such a violent act”. The concept has been linked to religious, socio-political, economic, and cultural factors. Even though terrorism originated from Islamic fanaticism, it is now driven by factors such as inequalities within the country and a lack among Nigerians in terms of livelihood (economic) resources, education or access to education, and good values.

For instance, terrorism in Nigeria is not a recent phenomenon; it started with the notorious Islamic sect in the northern part of Nigeria called Mataisine during the Alhaji Shehu Shagari civilian regime of the second republic, which was aborted by a military coup in December 1983 led by General Muhammadu Buhari. Terrorism reared its ugly head again during the Obasanjo civilian regime of the Fourth Republic, which witnessed religious riots in Plateau State in Northern Nigeria. In recent times, terrorism has assumed a political undertone, has been spearheaded by faceless Islamic insurgents based in the northern region of Nigeria called Boko Haram. It has claimed thousands of lives in the North since 2009.

Accordingly, some foreign observers have linked terrorism in Africa to a number of factors, which include political conflicts, unbalanced development that involves horizontal inequalities, religious and ethnic distrust, poor governance linked to leadership failure, and high levels of corruption (Kufour, 2012; Oluwarotimi, 2012).

Impact of Insecurity on Africa's Economic Development

After years of independence, most African countries are ranked among the poorest countries in the world and also rank low in all socio-economic indicators such as life expectancy, death rate, access to water, poverty rate, mortality rate, and crime rate, and still carry the tag of a developing economy. For instance, Nigeria is a classic illustration of an oxymoron, a poor country in the midst of abundant human and natural resources. This scenario has contributed to the security challenges that have bedevilled the region since her independence, with great consequences for socioeconomic development.

Without a doubt, there is no nation that can achieve socio-economic development in an environment of social and physical insecurity. Hence, any nation that is riddled with crisis and insecurity hardly makes progress. By so doing, genuine investors will be scared away from such countries. Sadly, the foreign direct investor profile of most African countries aptly reflects the dire economic consequences faced by a nation riddled with insecurity. By so doing, the foreign direct investments into the region drop remarkably due to the high level of insecurity and crisis, as no sane person will put his or her investment in a troubled zone, which in turn affects the regional economic development. Consequently, there is no investor, whether local or foreign, who will be motivated to invest in an unsafe and insecure environment. In a globalised world, investors are not only looking for high returns on their investments but also a safe haven for their investments. Thus, the alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has made the economy unattractive to foreign investors, and this has impacted negatively on economic growth and development.

The increasing challenge of insecurity in Africa has also been linked to the failure of leadership to deliver good governance and secure the welfare of people on the principles of freedom, equality, and justice. The ruling elites in Africa in both the military and democratic dispensation are dependent, parasitic, very corrupt in nature, and mal-administration (Ali, 2013). Their activities for decades have damaged economic growth and development. The inability of the government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives, properties, and the conduct of business and economic activities has led to resentment and disaffection among ethnic groups. This has resulted in ethnic violence, communal clashes, and religious violence in different parts of the country and has destroyed lives and properties, disrupted businesses and economic activities, and retarded economic growth and development in Nigeria.

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According to Ambulacra (2005), the problem of insecurity has a very damaging consequence of giving signals to the rest of the international community that Africa (and Nigeria in particular) is not a safe and secure place and, as such, not sustainable for economic investments and activities. Furthermore, the tourism potential in the region has threatened both tourists and industrial activities, causing potential investors to take their money to a place where there is peace and safety and not where the risk of being killed is high. Furthermore, insecurity in the African region has its effects and impacts on the psychological health and wellbeing of individuals and the state as a whole. For instance, when an individual feels unsafe, such a state of security may also affect his productivity. This no doubt affects the financial base of most African states and their economic growth as well as development.

Conclusion

Building resilient communication and supporting national development objectives mitigates the losses inflicted on countries due to insecurity. Particularly disturbing is the observation that conflict is always associated with underdevelopment or regression. Hence, the security of countries, no matter how advanced, is intricately linked to development not just within their borders but also in other countries and regions of the world. Responses to security threats cannot be limited to military action but should incorporate development solutions to entrench the peace dividend in communities, create societies that are more inclusive, and create conditions for sustained economic growth for national development.

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